

**ARDUINO BASED SMOKE AND GAS DETECTOR USING
MQ2 GAS SENSOR**

**BY
MBA JOSEPHINE ONYINYECHI
EBSU/2013/69451**

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SUPERVISOR: DR. CHINAGOLUM ITUMA

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this project work titled “**SMOKE AND GAS DETECTOR USING MQ2 GAS SENSOR**” was carried out by Mba Josephine Onyinyechi with the registration number of **EBSU/2013/69451** of the Department of Computer Science, Faculty of Sciences, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki and has not been submitted in any other institution in a part or whole for the award of any degree, diploma or certificate.

.....
MBA JOSEPHINE ONYINYECHI

.....
Date

APPROVAL

This project titled “**GAS AND SMOKE DETECTOR USING MQ2 GAS SENSOR**” is presented by **MBA JOSEPHINE ONYINYECHI** with the registration number **EBSU/2013/69451** respectively in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.) in department of Computer Science, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki by:

.....
Dr. Ituma Chinagolum
(Supervisor)

.....
Date

.....
Dr. Ajah I.A
(Head of Department)

.....
Date

.....
External supervisor

.....
Date

DEDICATION

All thanks to God Almighty for his infinite wisdom, knowledge, sound health which he made available to me all through the course of this project without which I wouldn't have accomplished this work. And also to my parents Mr. and Mrs.Mba Kalu for giving me the opportunity to acquire this knowledge.

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ABSTRACT

Both Residential and domestic occupancies requires a high measure of security as this is a great concern for all of us in this world. Arduino Based Smoke and gas detector using MQ2 gas Sensor is very useful in the detection of smoke and leakage of gas in homes, stations, cars, industries etc, so it is an important measure that will aid in the prevention of sudden fire outbreak in the above mentioned places. This project work is designed in such a way that it releases a warning signal whenever there is a detection of smoke or gas leakage as the gas may be via the alarming control panel. Arduino Uno is used as a major component in the project which incorporated of MQ2 Sensor, buzzer, Led as the major components. The sensor is connected to the circuit as well as the buzzer However, MQ2 module for smoke and gas sensor will be used for this project to ensure useful gas and smoke detection, as this will be capable of handling the detection of H₂, LPG, CH₄, CO, Alcohol, and Smoke. Finally, Arduino software is used was designed using the C/C++ programming language. Finally, we were able to achieve our set goals at the end of our project, this is because a system that is able to detect smoke and gas leakage was actualized.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Fire causes huge loss of lives and properties every year in Nigeria and some other parts of the world. Analyzing past fire incidents, facts are revealed. Some of the main causes are insufficient fire defense materials, electric short circuit from faulty electrical wiring, presence of inflammable materials, violation of fire safety and lack of adequate awareness etc. Some factories and recent buildings have proper installation and fire safety arrangements such as fire alarm, fire extinguishers, water supply system etc. But the argument is these conventional fire extinguishing systems are not enough to take prompt action during fire and save life. Traditional manual system does not ensure constant insurance from fire protection. Moreover, existing fire protection system could spread panic inside the whole building since it can only announce the presence. It only raises alarm whenever fire is detected at any place. Frightened people could start to run away haphazardly. As a result buildings full of workers in the factories women, children could be smashed by the outgoing pressure of the frightened crowd and injured severely. On the contrary, sometimes people do not realize the intensity of the fire and not willing to evacuate fire affected building quickly. It could lead a devastating result. (Md Iftekharul 2016)

Smoke and gas detector has become a fundamental component of the active fire protection strategy of most modern buildings, particularly residential occupancies. It is a device that detects and senses smoke and leakage of gas, typically as an indicator of fire. It will then issue a signal to a fire alarm control panel as part of fire alarm system, especially in commercial security devices or may issue a local audible or visual alarm in the household (Bukowski & Mulholland, 2001).

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of inflammable materials, violation of fire safety and lack of adequate awareness etc which could have been prevented by means of this device. Some factories and recent buildings have proper installation and fire safety arrangements such as fire alarm, fire extinguishers, water supply system etc. But the argument is this conventional fire extinguishing systems are not enough to take prompt action during fire and save life.

Traditional manual system does not ensure 24/7 monitoring from fire protection. Moreover, existing fire protection system could spread panic inside the whole building since it does not announce the location of fire or intensity. It only raises alarm whenever fire is detected at any place. Frightened people could start to run away haphazardly. On the contrary, sometimes people do not realize the intensity of the fire and not willing to evacuate fire affected building quickly and this could lead to a devastating result.

Fire detection has become a crucial aspect in design of buildings, both commercial and domestic, as opposed to about 70 years ago when automatic detection was rarely provided in buildings. Before introduction of smoke and gas alarms, fires resulted in the loss of human lives and damage of property and it was mainly attributed to lack of a mechanism for early detection of the resulting effect. This project work is presented so that it can minimize this hazard. Along with fire alarm this system announces locations of Smoke and gas leakage and is able to detect severity in order to interrupt fire disaster. To prevent fire from spreading: some efforts are extremely important. Such as: breaking electric circuits of the affected area, releases fire extinguishing gas on the hazard spot, calling fire service, inform promptly building monitoring committee by text messages or telephone calls. Smoke and Gas detector using MG2 sensor system takes prompt attempt to accomplish these tasks.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Fire outbreak in Nigeria has become a reoccurring event that has resulted to so many loss of life and properties as it is seen in the Sun and other newspapers constantly reporting about that. Hence the motivation is as follows;

1. Most of the existing system lacks the power to dictate smoke as a good indication of fire as faulty electrical wiring and other faulty electrical similar features could lead to fire disaster through the releasing of smoke.
2. Most of the existing system lacks the ability to dictate leakage of gas as an indication of fire in our homes (As seen in the case of domestic cooking cylinder left partially closed after cooking) and beyond.
3. Many solutions do not provide an easy-to-use computer interface to control and monitor home with respect to leakage of gas or smoke.
4. Most existing systems are not affordable for most users due to high costs and difficult maintenance.

1.3 Significance of study

Identification of a problem is the first step to solving it, the importance of this project work can help the stakeholders in many areas such as safeguarding of their property, by averting the fire through the help of the system which helps to trigger alarm to the user first by mere sensing of smoke and gas leakage, helping government to save money which they have budgeted for the compensation of such victims, and many other benefits which time may fail us not to mention.

1.4 Aim and Objectives

The aim this project is to design and implement Arduino based Smoke and gas detector system. The objectives include:

- 1) To develop a sensor module that will help to dictate the presence of smoke and gas leakage.
- 2) To develop a buzzer module that will trigger alarm to the property owner.
- 3) To develop a visual module (LED) that will indicate when smoke or leakage of gas is detected.

1.5 Scope of the project work

This project work focuses on how to design an Arduino based circuit for smoke and gas detection using MQ2 gas sensor. It activates an alarm when a substantive quantity of smoke or leakage of gas is sensed.

1.6 Definition of Terms

1. Block Diagram - a diagram of a system, in which the principal parts or functions are represented by blocks connected by lines that show the relationships of the blocks.
2. Circuit - a simplified conventional graphical representation of an electrical circuit.
3. Hardware - a general term for the physical artefacts of a technology.
4. LCD - digital display that uses liquid crystal cells that change reflectivity in an applied electric field; used for portable computer displays, watches, etc.
5. Microcontroller - a small computer on a single integrated circuit containing a processor core, memory, and programmable input/output peripherals.
6. Programming - the process of designing, writing, testing, debugging / troubleshooting, and maintaining the source code of computer programs.
7. Resistor – a two-terminal electric circuit component that offers opposition to an electric current. Resistors are normally designed and operated so that, with varying levels of current, variations of their resistance values are negligible.
8. Sensor - any device that receives a signal or stimulus (as heat or pressure or light or motion etc.) and responds to it in a distinctive manner.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Review of Detectors

Detectors can be of different types with various specific features depending upon different scenarios and demands. More or less these detectors can be categorized as heat or thermal detectors, smoke or gas detectors, infrared gas detectors, Semi-conductor gas detectors, and flame detectors (Cote, A. and Bugbee, P. 2003)

2.1.1 Heat or Thermal Type Detectors

Heat or thermal type detectors are the most primitive types of autonomous fire detectors, dating back to mid-1800. Most of these detectors are fixed temperature ones, which activates upon reaching a predefined temperature. Others include types, which activate whenever there is an abnormal rise in temperature in the premises. Thermal detectors are reliable, inexpensive, easy to maintain, and have lower false alarm rate. But these detectors are slow, and by the time they reach predefined detection point, damage could already been underway. Therefore these detectors are of limited use. (Nick Artim, 2007)

2.1.2 Infrared Gas detectors

IR detection has been well received by many industries, including the petrochemical industry. The major functional components of the analyzer are protected with optical parts. In other words, gas molecules interact only with a light beam McAvoy, T.J et al (2001). Only the sample cell and related components are directly exposed to the gas sample stream. These components can be treated, making them resistant to corrosion, and can be designed such that they are easily removable for maintenance or replacement. In its application the IR detector responds to radiation by generating a constant signal, which is considered the “zero” point for the source. Once the zero point is established and maintained, the span calibration is automatically taken care of. This is due to the fact that the absorption of radiation by the gas is always in the same proportion, regardless of its initial source intensity. Therefore, as long

as the zero point is maintained, the accuracy of the detector remains intact. This is one of the biggest advantages of IR technology. However, this detector requires extreme carefulness in order words any slight mistake from the user poses him to danger this is because of the calibration check which is an invaluable routine safety check that should not be eliminated from any periodic maintenance also the IR instruments used for this monitoring application are typically limited to the detection of higher concentrations (1% and above) of hydrocarbons and carbon monoxide. Carbon dioxide absorbs infrared radiation very strongly, and many monitors are available that can detect carbon dioxide in concentration ranges of 0.1% and higher. (Mulholland, G.W., 2003)

Fig1 An example of infrared gas sensor (Source Harzadous Monitor)

2.1.3 Semiconductor Gas or Smoke Detectors

These work by the principle of chemical reaction taking place between gas from fire incident and semiconductor material present inside the sensor. The semiconductor material used in these sensors is metal oxides, generally Tin dioxide (SnO_2), Tungsten oxide (WO_3), etc. Under normal circumstances, the surface potential acts as a potential barrier to restrict electron flow within the sensor circuitry. However, the deoxidizing gases from fire incidents diminish the oxygen surface density, and thereby reduce barrier potential to permit electron flow. The associated electrical circuitry detects the rise in conductivity due to electron flow, and activates alarm to undertake necessary measures (Figaro Engineering Inc. 2014).

These semiconductor sensors have wide range of applications for their advantageous features. They are small, compact, inexpensive, easy to install and maintain. These metal oxide type detectors are aptly used to detect fire incidents involving combustible gas, LP gas, methane,

propane, alcohol, carbon monoxide etc. for their reliability. However, these detection systems are complex and expensive. (Meacham, et al., 2006)

Fig 2 Semiconductor gas or smoke detector (Source Isweek.com)

2.1.4 Flame Type Detectors

Flame type detectors are sophisticated equipment to detect the flame phenomena of a fire. These detectors have various types depending on the light wavelength they use. Such as, ultraviolet, near infrared, infrared, and combination of UV/IR type detectors.

UV detectors generally work with wavelengths shorter than 300 nm. This type of detectors can detect fires and explosions situations within 3 - 4 milliseconds from the UV radiation emitted from the incident. However, to reduce false alarm triggered by UV sources such as lightning, arc welding etc. a time delay is often included in the UV flame detector. The near Infrared sensor or visual flame detectors work with wavelengths between 0.7 to 1.1 μm . One of the most reliable technologies available for fire detection, namely multiple channel or pixel array sensors, monitors flames in the near IR band. The Infrared (IR) flame detectors work within the infrared spectral band (700 nm - 1 mm). Usual response time of these detectors is 3 - 5 seconds. Also, there is UV and IR combined flame detectors, which compare the threshold signal in two ranges to detect fire and minimize false alarms (Schifiliti et al 2011).

Flame detectors are expensive and complex, though they provide very reliable and accurate response. They can operate in highly sensitive environment where other detectors can't be

used. Aircraft maintenance facilities, fuel loading platforms, mines, refineries, high-tech industries etc. use these flame detectors for safety. (Encyclopaedia 2013).

Fig 3: Triple Sensor Flame Detector Source (Source Horizon)

2.1.5 Smoke or Gas Detectors

Safelincs (2000) stated that Smoke or gas detectors, a relatively newer invention, became widespread during 1970's and 1980's. These detectors usually detect fire in early flaming or smouldering stages. These detectors can be of different types having different operation principles, namely—optical or photoelectric detectors, ionization detectors, air sampling detectors etc. Each of these types has specific applications in specific circumstances (Cote A. and Bugbee P. 1988).

Photoelectric or optical smoke detectors include various components, mainly, a light source (usually an infrared LED), and a lens to converge light rays into a beam, and a photodiode. In normal condition, the light beam passes straight. But whenever smoke interrupts the path of light, scatters fraction of light into the photodiode, the smoke detector is activated. This method of detection can detect fires that begin with long duration of smouldering aptly. Ionization smoke detectors are based on ionization from radioactive elements like americium-241. This radioactive isotope emits alpha particles into an ionization chamber, which comprises of electrodes. The alpha particles ionize the air inside the chamber, resulting current flow between the electrodes. Now, whenever smoke particles from a nearby fire passes through the chamber, the ions get attached to smoke particles, and thereby interrupts the current flow between the electrodes, and activates the detector. This type of detectors is more suited to rapid flaming fire outbursts, unlike the photoelectric detectors, which responds

better to smouldering stages. Ionization detectors might perform better where there is risk of fast flaming fire, whereas photoelectric detectors react better to cases of slow smouldering, like electrical or furnishing fire. Ionization devices are weaker in scenarios where air-flow is high. Ionization type detectors are cheaper than photoelectric ones, they have more chance of better alarm than the photoelectric detectors (Bukowski, R.W., et al 2007). However, ionization based detectors have safety issues and possess appealing to the environment. Air sampling detectors have applications in very sensitive areas, as they can detect very fine smoke particles. These detectors are mostly air aspirating type systems. Generally they comprise a control unit, and a network of sampling tubes or pipes. The control unit consists of detection chamber, an aspiration fan, and necessary operation circuitry. Since this type of detectors are very sensitive and fast responding, they have applications in high-value and critical areas, such as, aesthetic galleries, archives, vaults, server rooms, high-tech organizations, etc. These sensors have wide range of applications for their advantageous features. They are small, compact, inexpensive, easy to install and maintain. These detectors are aptly used to detect fire incidents involving combustible gas, LP gas, methane, propane, alcohol, carbon monoxide etc. for their reliability. These features make this detector best suited for our project and hence we opted for it in our system.

Fig4: Fire Smoke sensor detector (Source e-bay)

2.2 Review of Related Work

Prof. James (2003) carried out a study on evaluation of Smoke Detector Response Estimation Methods. This study was to assess the uncertainty associated with these estimation methods.

Experimental data was used to evaluate recommended alarm thresholds and to quantify the associated error. With few exceptions, less than 50 percent of the predicted alarm times occurred within ± 60 seconds of the experimental alarms. Unfortunately this system took this time (± 60 sec) because the sensor was not placed close to where it can sense the smoke.

Omar (2014) designed an intelligent home system using the GSM network. He stated that the system is to monitor heat and gas values in the home and determine whether there are any high proportions. To achieve this he used GSM module to receive SMS alert from the system, the sounding buzzer, SDRAM to save events to a specific text file and also a sensor that turns off lights automatically when there is no one in the room and then the system monitors outside weather. However this system is so complex and the materials used to achieve the project are expensive but the use of Smoke and Gas sensor stand as advantage with a minimal cost in its implementation.

Asif et al (2014) carried out a study which focuses on Fire-Detectors Review and Design of an Automated, Quick Responsive Fire-Alarm System Based on SMS. In this work a review of existing fire-detector types has been carried out along with the development of a low cost, portable, and reliable microcontroller based automated fire alarm system for remotely alerting any fire incidents in household or industrial premises. A SIM300CZ GSM kit based network module, capable of operating in standard GSM bands, has been used to send alert messages. The system is implemented on printed circuit board (PCB) and tested under different experimental conditions to evaluate its performances. However this system is complex considering all that are involved to achieve it.

Md Iftkharul et al (2016) developed and implemented An Intelligent Fire Detection and Mitigation System Safe from Fire (SFF). It takes input signals from various sensors placed in different position of the monitored area, and combines integrated fuzzy logic to identify fire breakout locations and severity. Data fusion algorithm facilitates the system to discard deceptive fire situations such as: cigarette smoke, welding etc. During the fire hazard SFF notifies the fire service and others by text messages and telephone calls. Along with ringing

fire alarm it announces the fire affected locations and severity. To prevent fire from spreading it breaks electric circuits of the affected area, releases the extinguishing gas pointing to the exact fire locations. The use of sensors in different position of the monitored area, combining with the use of integrated fuzzy logic in the implementation of this project, makes it a bit complex when compared to our proposed system that uses just one sensor in its implementation.

Ng'ang'a (2015) Developed and implemented a smoke alarm. This project therefore seeks to design a microcontroller based smoke alarm that will continuously monitor the presence of significant amount of smoke and activate an alarm to prompt a safety measure to contain the situation. There is also an extra functionality of LCD display for visual alert. This is a good system that is worthy of implementation but the use of LCD over LED in the visual display made the system complex when compare to our project.

Muhammad (2014) carried out a project research on how to make an IoT smoke detection system in which MQ-2 smoke sensor was used to sense if there is smoke nearby. If smoke is nearby, then the buzzer will start beeping and the red LED will light up and a warning will be displayed on a web page which will create using ESP8266 module. The webpage is made accessible using any connected device like a mobile, tablet, or PC. The module used here for information display is expensive.

2.3 Review of MQ gas Sensors

The MQ sensor finds application in gas leak and smoke detection application as stated by R (Pitarma et al., 2017), their major advantageous features include:

- High sensitivity
- Fast response
- Wide detection range
- Stable performance and long life
- Simple drive circuit

Below are the various MQ series sensors and their target gas of detection

Model	Target Gas
MQ2	General combustible gas including smoke.
MQ3	Alcohol
MQ4	Natural gas, Methane
MQ5	LPG, Natural gas, Coal gas
MQ6	LPG, Propane
MQ7	Carbon Monoxide
MQ8	Hydrogen
MQ9	CO and Combustible gas
MQ216	Natural gas\ Coal gas
MQ306A	LPG, Propane
MQ309A	CO, Flammable gas
MQ303A	Alcohol
MQ131	Ozone O ₃
MQ135	Air Quality Control(NH ₃ , Benzene, Alcohol, Smoke)
MQ136	H ₂ S
MQ137	Ammonia
MQ138	Mellow, Benzene, Aldehyde, Ketone, Ester

Table 1: MQ Series Sensors

The reason why we have decided to use MQ2 for this project work is because; it is the most suitable and readily available for smoke and gas detection.

According to voltage G Marrques et al., 2016, MQ2 sensor is a flammable gas and smoke sensor which detects the concentrations of combustible gas in the air and outputs reading as an analogue voltage. It is sensitive to a wide range of gases and is used at room temperature. Some modules have a built-in variable resistor to adjust the sensitivity of the sensor. It falls

under the category of electromechanical gas detectors which work by allowing gases to diffuse through a porous membrane to an electrode where it is either chemically oxidized or reduced. The amount of current produced is determined by how much of the gas is oxidized at the electrode, indicating concentration of the gas. However, this type of sensors is subject to corrosive elements or chemical contamination and may last only 1-2 years before a replacement is required. For MQ2, the sensitive material used is SnO₂, whose conductivity is lower in clean air. Its conductivity increases as the concentration of combustible gases increases. The output voltage, which is analogue in nature, can be used to activate a buzzer by interfacing it with a microcontroller, Arduino or Raspberry Pi.

For the purpose of design of the smoke detector circuit for this project, the MQ2 sensor was chosen due to the following advantageous features:

- Wide detecting scope
- Availability
- Stable and long life
- Fast response
- Low cost
- Simple drive circuit

2.3 Review of LCD (Liquid Crystal Display)

According to Matt (2015) liquid crystal display, or LCD, is a video display that utilizes the light modulating properties of liquid crystals to display pictures or text on a screen. We have graphical and character LCD's; Character LCDs are ideal for displaying text. They can also be configured to display small icons but the icons must be only 5x7 pixels, while the graphical LCD has one big grid of pixels (in this case 128x64 of them) - It can display text but its best at displaying images. Graphical LCDs tend to be larger, more expensive, and difficult to use and need many more pins because of the complexity added. Since their invention in 1964, LCD screens have grown to be used in a very wide variety of applications; one way to utilize an LCD is with an Arduino microcontroller. By wiring an Arduino microcontroller to the pins of an LCD display it is possible to program the microcontroller to

display a desired text string or image on the screen. However we use LED technology in our project for such display indications instead of LCD because of its complexity and cost.

Graphic LCD Vs Character LCD

Fig 5: Graphic LCD (Source LadyAda)

Fig 6: Character LCD (Source LadyAda)

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY AND SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 Methodology

A system development methodology refers to the framework that is used to structure, plan, and control the process of developing an information system. A wide variety of such frameworks have evolved over the years, each with its own recognized strengths and weaknesses. One system development methodology is not necessarily suitable for use by all projects. Each of the available methodologies is best suited to specific kinds of projects, based on various technical, organizational, project and team considerations. This project has considered each of the major prescribed methodologies in context with the project's, applications, and technical environments. As a result, the project requires the use of modular methodology for Smoke and Gas detector systems development, as appropriate.

3.2 Types of Methodology

There are many types of methodologies, some are discussed below;

- Waterfall Model
- V-Shaped Model
- Prototyping Model
- Spiral Model
- Modular
- Agile Model

3.2.1 Waterfall Methodology

The waterfall Model is the oldest type of methodology ever used and follows a linear sequential flow. In which progress is seen as flowing steadily downwards (like a waterfall) through the phases of software implementation. This means that any phase in the development process begins only if the previous phase is complete. The waterfall approach does not define the process to go back to the previous phase to handle changes in

requirement. The waterfall approach is the earliest approach and most widely known that was used for software development.

Fig 7: Diagram of waterfall methodology (Source Ide-Smith)

3.2.2 Modular Methodology

According to engineering Dictionary a modular technique or design is a technique to the construction of an equipment, systems, programs, and the like, in which independently prepared and self-contained units, or modules, are combined to produce the final product.

A modular system is characterized by functional partitioning into discrete scalable, reusable modules; rigorous use of well-defined modular interfaces; and making use of industry standards for interfaces.

Fig 8: Diagram of Modular Methodology (Source Ide-Smith)

3.3 Choice of Methodology

Just as stated earlier modular design", is a design approach that subdivides a system into smaller parts called modules or skids, which can be independently created and then used in different systems.

I choose this methodology because it allows for simultaneously developing and testing the various components and also helps disintegrate a large and complex system into more manageable parts, also called modular principle, modular technique, modular design and building block approach.

Besides reduction in cost (due to less customization, and shorter learning time), and flexibility in design, modularity offers other benefits such as augmentation (adding new solution by merely plugging in a new module), and exclusion.

3.4 Method of Data Collection.

Information gathering is the formal process of acquiring relevant data and information pertaining to the system in study. Below are some methods of data collection.

i Study of Operational Document

This is a very crucial means of data collection which involves reviewing all readily available materials. These materials can include internal company information (Organizational charts, administrative procedure manual, job descriptions, training manuals, company's mission statement and strategies plan and official memoranda), relevant trade publications, newspapers, magazines, annual reports, on-line databases, and other published materials. The user often uses this method when the validity of data collected through other methods is in question or when the complexity of certain aspects of the system prevents a clear explanation.

ii On-Site Observation

Observation is the systematic description of events, behaviours, and artefacts in the social setting chosen for study (Marshall & Rossman 2007). This is another important means of acquiring information. This is because, many times, some technical details of how operational processes are carried out are not always documented. An on the site observation would serve as an eye-opener to understanding how operational process are physically carried out. This would entail being bodily present and involved in operations hence monitoring the processes.

iii Interview Method

This is a way to get in-depth and comprehensive information from individuals face to face. It involves one person interviewing (interviewer) another person (interviewee) for detailed information. Typically there would be a well-articulated set of questions by the interviewer. This ensures that he is not emotionally carried away by the interview.

iv Questionnaire and Survey

Questionnaires are special purpose documents that allow the analyst to collect information and opinion from respondents. This method of information gathering requires a well-articulated set of written questions called a questionnaire. The questionnaires with appropriate cover letters are returns back to the researcher/analyst hence maintaining a uniform response format like strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly Disagree. One of the disadvantages noticed in questionnaire method is that people feels so reluctant in returning the questionnaire given to them and those who do might be representative of the originally selected sample (Abdul, 2004)

Surveys are carried out in either of the below methods which includes; Telephone survey method, Mail survey method and Email/Internet surveys

This project work employed the method of observation and documentary method extensively because of their relevance, quick and efficient means of providing information vital and appropriate to the accomplishment of the project work at hand.

3.5 Analysis of the existing System

According Mykh (2013), the oldest method used before and even now to extinguish or control fire disaster was the use of manual fire extinguisher. The first fire extinguisher of which there is any record was patented in England in 1723 by Ambrose Godfrey, a celebrated chemist at that time. It consisted of a cask of fire-extinguishing liquid containing a pewter chamber of gunpowder. This was connected with a system of fuses which were ignited, exploding the gunpowder and scattering the solution. This device was probably used to a limited extent, as Bradley's Weekly Messenger for November 7, 1729, refers to its efficiency in stopping a fire in London. The modern fire extinguisher was invented by British Captain George William Manby in 1818; it consisted of a copper vessel of 3 gallons (13.6 liters) of pearl ash (potassium carbonate) solution contained within compressed air.

The soda-acid extinguisher was first patented in 1866 by Francois Carlier of France, which mixed a solution of water and sodium bicarbonate with tartaric acid, producing the propellant CO₂ gas. A soda-acid extinguisher was patented in the U.S. in 1881 by Almon M. Granger. His extinguisher used the reaction between sodium bicarbonate solution and sulfuric acid to expel pressurized water onto a fire. A vial of concentrated sulfuric acid was suspended in the cylinder. Depending on the type of extinguisher, the vial of acid could be broken in one of two ways. One used a plunger to break the acid vial, while the second released a lead stopple that held the vial closed. Once the acid was mixed with the bicarbonate solution, carbon dioxide gas was expelled and thereby pressurized the water. The pressurized water was forced from the canister through a nozzle or short length of hose and the host of others which time may fail me to mention.

A fire extinguisher is an active fire protection device used to extinguish or control small fires, often in emergency situations. Typically, a fire extinguisher consists of a hand-held cylindrical pressure vessel containing an agent which can be discharged to extinguish a fire. Fire extinguishers manufactured with non-cylindrical pressure vessels also exist, but are less common. In the United States, fire extinguishers in all buildings other than houses are generally required to be serviced and inspected by a fire protection service company at least annually. Some jurisdictions require more frequent service for fire extinguishers. The servicer places a tag on the extinguisher to indicate the type of service performed (annual inspection, recharge, and new fire extinguisher).

3.5.1 Types of fire extinguishers

There are two main types of fire extinguishers: stored-pressure and cartridge-operated. In stored pressure units, the expellant is stored in the same chamber as the fire fighting agent itself. Depending on the agent used, different propellants are used. With dry chemical extinguishers, nitrogen is typically used; water and foam extinguishers typically use air. Stored pressure fire extinguishers are the most common type. Cartridge-operated extinguishers contain the expellant gas in a separate cartridge that is punctured prior to discharge, exposing the propellant to the extinguishing agent. This type is not as common, used primarily in areas such as industrial facilities, where they receive higher-than-average use. They have the advantage of simple and prompt recharge, allowing an operator to discharge the extinguisher, recharge it, and return to the fire in a reasonable amount of time. Unlike stored pressure types, these extinguishers use compressed carbon dioxide instead of nitrogen, although nitrogen cartridges are used on low temperature (-60 rated) models.

Fig 9: Stored pressure type of extinguisher

Fig 10: Cartridge type of extinguisher

3.5.2 Installations

Fire extinguishers are typically fitted in buildings at an easily accessible location, such as against a wall in a high-traffic area. They are also often fitted to motor vehicles, watercraft, and aircraft - this is required by law in many jurisdictions, for identified classes of vehicles. Under NFPA 10 all commercial vehicles must carry at least one fire extinguisher, with size/UL rating depending on type of vehicle and cargo (i.e., fuel tankers typically must have a 20 lb (9.1 kg), while most others can carry a 5 lb (2.3 kg)). The revised NFPA 10 created criteria on the placement of "fast flow extinguishers" in locations such as those storing and transporting pressurized flammable liquids and pressurized flammable gas or areas with possibility of three dimensional class B hazards are required to have "fast flow extinguishers" as required by NFPA 5.5.1.1. Varying classes of competition vehicles require fire extinguishing systems, the simplest requirements being a 1A:10BC hand-held portable extinguisher mounted to the interior of the vehicle.

Fig 11: Fire extinguisher fitted to the passenger seat

3.6 Problem of the existing System

1. Traditional manual system (i.e. manual fire extinguisher) does not ensure 24/7 monitoring from fire protection.
2. This device is only use to extinguish or control small fires, often in emergency situations.
3. It is not intended for use on an out-of-control fire, such as one which has reached the ceiling, endangers the user (i.e., no escape route, smoke, explosion hazard, etc.), or otherwise requires the expertise of a fire department.

3.6.1 Location and Functionality

1. Functionality of a manual fire extinguisher starts when there is already a fire outbreak, neither does it posses the intelligence of giving direction on where the incidence is taking place, allowing them to get their quicker.
2. A manual fire extinguisher does not provide the earliest warning as afore mentioned, which is imperative when combating a fire and this makes one vulnerable to extensive damage and danger. This hinders one from discovering the need to evacuate before time, even if it's by seconds. A fire can start in any room and it can spread at any rate. Even if you aren't in the exact room where it started, you'll still have knowledge of it.

3.7 Analysis of the Proposed System

The proposed system is designed to solve the problem of the existing system by means of releasing alarm once there is a sense of smoke or leakage of gas to some quantified level via

the means of buzzer which is been controlled by the Arduino board. The Arduino program is designed to regulate the change in the atmospheric nature of the environment where the system is installed and then send a signal to MQ2 sensor once there is a change in the atmospheric level by means of smoke or gas to a given threshold value

3.7.1 How the Proposed System Works

One of the components MQ2 sensor been controlled by the Arduino detects the presence of flammable smoke and gases like methane, propane, alcohol, butane etc. in the surrounding where it is installed. If the level of gas or smoke goes beyond the threshold values (i.e. the point at which detection starts) which is preset in code, the Red Led will start glow and buzzer (ie alarm) is activated and in safe condition green led will be glowing while the buzzer is deactivated.

3.7.2 Avoiding False Alarm by the System

Although there are many things which can lead to setting off false alarm by the system but one of the beautiful things we have implemented in this work in other to avoid the production of false alarm by the system is to set a threshold value (i.e. the point at which detection of gas or smoke starts) as we stated earlier to some reasonable high and acceptable value measured in ppm such that the system will not be able to react to a mere smoke or gas that is not capable of producing a fire example is the cigarette smoke.

Other things that can lead to production of false alarm by the system include the following:

1. Humidity
2. Dust and insects
3. Strong chemical odours
4. Your detector's location
5. Power issues

Cause 1: Humidity

High humidity can cause a smoke detector to go off because the detector can mistake humid air for smoke. We're especially susceptible to this problem in Florida where humidity is often 70% or higher,

Solution: Close your windows and doors to block the outside humidity from reaching the smoke detector. Also, make sure your detector is **10+ feet away** from rooms with high humidity like bathrooms and laundry rooms.

Cause 2: Dust and Insects

Dust that finds its way into your smoke detector can trigger the alarm because the detector mistakes those particles for smoke.

Solution: Remove your smoke detector and clean it to remove debris or dead insects. Also, see the solution for Cause #1 about switching from an ionization smoke detector to a photoelectric smoke detector.

Cause 3: Strong chemicals and odours

Have you painted your home or polished your furniture recently? In addition to agitating our nostrils, these strong chemicals like ammonia and paint can also set off your smoke detector.

Solution: Avoid using strong chemicals in areas that are close to your smoke detectors. If you do need to paint or use chemicals with ammonia, be sure to properly ventilate your home.

Cause 4: Your detectors Location

Some areas in your home can trigger your smoke detector's alarm. You'll want to make sure your smoke detectors are...

- **20+ feet** away from appliances like your oven, furnace and fireplace
- **3+ feet** away from air conditioning and heating vents
- Not inside your garage. Automotive fumes or strong chemicals can set off the alarm, so we'd recommend going with a heat alarm inside your garage instead.

Cause #5: Power issues

Power issues that could cause your alarm to activate include the following:

- **Power interruptions:** AC/DC smoke alarms may go off briefly until your power comes back on.
- **A loose hot wire:** You'll need an electrician to tighten the wires if this is what's tripping your alarm.
- **A large current load on the same circuit as your alarm:** High wattage appliances like vacuum cleaners, space heaters or hair dryers that are on the same circuit as your alarm can overload your circuit, trip the power and cause your alarm to go off. Avoid putting too many high wattage appliances on the same circuit as your smoke detectors.
- **An interconnected alarm system:** You've heard the phrase "one rotten apple spoils the whole bunch," right? Well, the same applies to an interconnected alarm system, where all of your smoke detectors are all on the same electrical currents. If one goes off, they'll all go off. If you're having problems with false alarms, contact an electrician to change your alarms to separate units.

3.7.3 Advantages of the proposed System

This system has the capability of providing early warning benefit. The fire alarms can be installed just about anywhere in a commercial building and best of all the fire safety measure is highly cost effective for smoke and fire protection. Early warning is essential to effective fire safety because fires can occur anytime and anyplace. We highly recommend having fire alarms (i.e. Smoke and gas detectors) installed on every floor of your commercial business because a fire can ignite even when people are not within a room or section of the building.

In addition, this early warning signal is extremely important to life safety for the following reasons:

1. Increases evacuation time for building occupants before a fire spreads out of control.
2. Gives an early warning signal to the occupants.

3. This early warning signal is extremely important to life; emergency medical help can be immediately sent out to those in need.
4. Fire department personnel can help people exit the building safely incase there is a sense of fire disaster that is so severe.

3.8 Block diagram of the proposed system

Fig 12: block diagram of the proposed system

CHAPTER FOUR

SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

The main objective of this project work is to design and implement an Arduino based circuit which will be capable of dictating the presence of smoke and gas leakage which will then trigger alarm via the buzzer. The design of this system is been divided into hardware design and Software design. We use MQ 2 sensor module and buzzer for the hardware design and we connected these Components with microcontroller. The Arduino software is downloaded from www.arduino.cc and C/C++ programmable language is used.

4.1 Hardware design

The circuitry design and analysis

Figure 13: Full Circuit Design

Mainly we use four major components for designing a full control system. The MQ2 module that senses signal which serves as input to the Arduino board, Alarm device connected to Arduino Uno board, the LED module which is useful for visual warnings and power control circuit. The output will shown by the glowing of the Red LED with the alarm.

Component Requirements

1. MQ-2 gas sensor
2. Buzzer
3. Breadboard
4. 220 ohms Resistor
5. Red and Green LED
6. 9v Battery and clip
7. Arduino Nano

Like we mentioned earlier, the design of this project is in two parts; one is the hardware design and the other is the software design. We used, Buzzer, Breadboard, MQ-2 gas sensor, Red and Green LED, 9v Battery and clip for the hardware design and we connected them to the Arduino Nano. We realized the Software design by downloading the Arduino software from *www.arduino.cc* and the programming language used is C++ programming language.

Review of the Components Used In the Project:

4.1.1 MQ-2 GAS SENSOR

MQ-2 gas sensor detects the presence of flammable gases like methane, butane, Propane, Alcohol etc including smoke. It is with low cost and suitable for different application. Features of MQ-2 gas include the following; wide detecting scope, fast response and High sensitivity, stable and long life, and simple drive circuit. Its area of applications includes; domestic gas leakage detector, industrial Combustible gas detector and portable gas detector.

Fig 14: MQ-2 gas sensor (Source Seed)

Specifications

Parameter	Value
Gas detection	Combustible gas and Smoke
Standard encapsulation	bakelite
Concentration	300-10000ppm

Table 1: MQ-2 Specifications

Interfaces

Pin No	Symbol	Descriptions
1.	DOUT	Digital output
2.	AOUT	Analog output
3.	GND	Power ground
4.	VCC	Positive power supply(2.5-5.0V)

Table 2: Interfaces

Precautions

Following conditions must be prohibited;

1 Exposed to organic silicon steam

Organic silicon steam cause sensors invalid, sensors must be avoid exposing to silicon bond, fixture, silicon latex, putty or plastic contain silicon environment

2 High Corrosive gas

If the sensor is exposed to high concentration corrosive gas (such as H₂Sz, SOX, Cl₂, HCl etc), it will not only result in corrosion of sensors structure, also it cause sincere sensitivity attenuation.

3 Alkali, Alkali metals salt, halogen pollution

The sensors performance will be changed badly if sensors be sprayed polluted by alkali metals salt especially brine, or be exposed to halogen such as fluorine.

4 Touch water

Sensitivity of the sensors will be reduced when spattered or dipped in water.

5 Freezing

Do avoid icing on sensor surface, otherwise sensor would lose sensitivity.

6 Applied voltage higher

Applied voltage on sensor should not be higher than stipulated value, otherwise it cause down-line or heater damaged, and bring on sensors' sensitivity characteristic changed badly.

7 Voltage on wrong pins

For 6 pins sensor, if apply voltage on 1、3 pins or 4、6 pins, it will make lead broken, and without signal when apply on 2、4 pins

Following conditions must be avoided

1 Water Condensation

Indoor conditions, slight water condensation will affect sensors performance lightly. However, if water condensation on sensors surface and keep a certain period, sensor' sensitivity will be decreased.

2 Used in high gas concentration

No matter the sensor is electrified or not, if long time placed in high gas concentration, it will affect sensors characteristic.

3 Long time storage

The sensors resistance produce reversible drift if it's stored for long time without electrify, this drift is related with storage conditions. Sensors should be stored in airproof without silicon gel bag with clean air.

For the sensors with long time storage but no electrify, they need long aging time for stability before using.

4 Long time exposed to adverse environment

No matter the sensors electrified or not, if exposed to adverse environment for long time, such as high humidity, high temperature, or high pollution etc, it will affect the sensors performance badly.

5 Vibration

Continual vibration will result in sensors down-lead response then rapture. In transportation or assembling line, pneumatic screwdriver/ultrasonic welding machine can lead this vibration.

6 Concussion

If sensors meet strong concussion, it may lead its lead wire disconnected.

7 Usage

For sensor, handmade welding is optimal way. If use wave crest welding should meet the following conditions:

Soldering flux: Rosin soldering flux contains least chlorine

Speed: 1-2 Meter/ Minute

Warm-up temperature: 100 ± 20

Welding temperature: 250 ± 10 time pass wave crest welding machine

If disobey the above using terms, sensors sensitivity will be reduced.

How does it Work?

The voltage that the sensor outputs changes accordingly to the smoke/gas level that exists in the atmosphere. The sensor outputs a voltage that is proportional to the concentration of smoke/gas.

In other words, the relationship between voltage and gas concentration is the following:

- a) The greater the gas concentration, the greater the output voltage
- b) The lower the gas concentration, the lower the output voltage

Fig 15: MQ2 sensor workability (Source Seeed)

4.1.2 BUZZER

A buzzer is any alarming devices which produces an audio signal over an event. It may be mechanical, electromechanical or piezoelectric. Types of buzzers includes; alarm devices, timers and confirmation of users input such as a mouse click or key stroke. We also have Mechanical, Electromechanical and Piezoelectric divisions of buzzer.

1 Mechanical

A joy buzzer is a typical example of a mechanical buzzer, they requires drivers to operate and are purely mechanical.

2 Electromechanical

Electromechanical type of a buzzer is an earlier used device which uses a relay connected to interrupt its own actuating current, causing the contacts to buzz.

3 Piezoelectric

These types are driven by an oscillating electronic circuit or other audio signal source, driven with a piezoelectric audio amplifier. Sounds usually indicates that a button has been pressed or a click, a ring or a beep.

Fig 16: Buzzer (Source Farhek)

4.1.3 BREADBOARD

The technology of breadboard came as advancement over the early wire-wrap technique which is a very complex and complicating process that involves wrapping wires around conductive posts attached to a perfboard /protoboard.

Breadboard is so called because when electronics were big and bulky, people would grab their mom's breadboard, a few nails or thumbtacks, and start connecting wires onto the board to give themselves a platform on which to build their circuits. Since then, electronic components have gotten a lot smaller, and we've come up with better ways to connect circuits.

Fig 17: Breadboard (Source Farhek)

4.1.4 LED

A light-emitting diode (LED) is a semiconductor diode which glows when a voltage is applied to it. It is a two-lead semiconductor light source. It is a p-n junction diode, which emits light when activated. When a suitable voltage is applied to the leads, electrons are able to recombine with electron holes within the device, releasing energy in the form of photons.

This effect is called electroluminescence, and the color of the light (corresponding to the energy of the photon) is determined by the energy band gap of the semiconductor.

This figure shows a typical red and green Led.

Fig 18: light-emitting diode (LED) (Source Farhek)

4.1.5 LOAD RESISTOR

The sensor needs a load-resistor at the output to ground. Its value could be from 2kOhm to 47kOhm. The lower the value, the less sensitive and the higher the value, the less accurate for higher concentration of gas, if only one specific gas is measured, the load-resistor can be calibrated by applying a known concentration of that gas. If the sensor is used to measure any gas (Like in an air quality detector) the load-resistor could be set for a value of about 1v output with clean air.

Fig 19: Resistor (Source trossenrobotics)

4.1.6 ARDUINO UNO

The Arduino Uno is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328. It has 14 digital input/output pins (of which 6 can be used as PWM outputs), 6 analog inputs, a 16 MHz crystal oscillator, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It contains everything needed to support the microcontroller; simply connect it to a computer with a USB cable or power it with an AC-to-DC adapter or battery to get started.

4.1.6.1 Power:

The Arduino Uno can be powered via the USB connection or with an external power supply. The power source is selected automatically. External (non-USB) power can come either from an AC-to-DC adapter or battery. The adapter can be connected by plugging a 2.1mm center-positive plug into the board's power jack. Leads from a battery can be inserted in the Gnd and Vin pin headers of the POWER connector. The board can operate on an external supply of 6 to 20 volts. If supplied with less than 7V, however, the 5V pin may supply less than five volts and the board may be unstable. If using more than 12V, the voltage regulator may overheat and damage the board. The recommended range is 7 to 12 volts.

The power pins are as follows:

- 1 **VIN:** The input voltage to the Arduino board when it's using an external power source (as opposed to 5 volts from the USB connection or other regulated power source). You can supply voltage through this pin, or, if supplying voltage via the power jack, access it through this pin.
- 2 **5V:** The regulated power supply used to power the microcontroller and other components on the board. This can come either from VIN via an on-board regulator, or be supplied by USB or another regulated 5V supply.
- 3 **3V3:** A 3.3 volt supply generated by the on-board regulator. Maximum current draw is 50 mA.
- 4 **GND:** Ground pins.

Figure 20: Arduino uno ATmega328 (Source: <http://www.trossenrobotics.com/p/Arduino-uno.aspx>)

4.2 Software Design

Software design is divided into two parts. First we write the Arduino program in Arduino software. Then we compile it to the Arduino hardware. This Arduino command control the Arduino hardware and other circuit connection. For making connection between Arduino and MQ-2 sensor module

4.2.1 The Flowchart Diagram Of The Proposed System

Fig 21: Flowchart Diagram of proposed system

4.2.2 System Implementation

All the parts are connected as circuit design. Then we upload the programming code in the Arduino and we get positive result. It works properly according to our design.

4.2.3 Development of the whole system

Step 1

Firstly we connect Arduino in bread board to MQ2 module, we interfaced it with the system to check its functionality

Fig 22 Connecting the MQ2 module with the Arduino Uno

Step 2

Then we move on to connecting the MQ2 sensor which senses and detect smoke and leakage with the Red and Blue LED which gives a visual display of light when smoke and gas is detected above a given range

Fig 23 Connecting MQ2 Sensor Module with the LEDs

Step 3

Then finally the whole system was implemented by connecting all of the components with the Buzzer for alarming purposes then interfacing it with the system.

Fig 24 Development of the system

CHAPTER FIVE

SYSTEM TESTING, INTEGRATION AND DEPLOYMENT

5.1 Integration Testing

After the project construction and connection there was need to ascertain that the components has been properly connected in order to work effectively as specified so as to evaluate the system compliance with the specified requirements. This test helped to expose defects in the interfaces and in the interaction integrated components or systems.

5.1.1 Component Integration Testing

Various components of the system were tested individually to ensure that they are working effectively before coupling them together into a system. This was done to ensure that effectiveness of the interfaces and a good interaction between the integrated components without a trace of error. Among the tested components includes resistors, buzzer, MQ2 sensor, Led etc.

5.1.2 System Integration Testing

The integration of the systems were tested and certified accurate and was also tested after been packaged; it interfaces were finally tested to ascertain it compliance to external organizations. After various adjustments on the components placements to achieve a required result, the system was disassembled. Each components connecting to the Arduino board was permanently soldered to the Vero board. This was done with carefulness to avoid error in the result.

5.1.3 Test Plan

Test plan describing the scope, approach, resources and schedule of the intended test activities was developed to help verify that the completed designed system is perfectly performing as was indicated in the circuit and system design. This is achieved by connecting the circuit to the power source or to the system using the USB power cable, When this is

done immediately the arduino board, MQ2 sensor and the green Led were powered on indicating that the system is in good working condition although this was not achieved immediately but after some minor modifications, the desired effect was gotten.

5.1.4 Final Test Result

This test was done at the point where the system has already started working perfectly, but was carried out to obtain 100% confidence that it might not fail.

So at this point the final designs were made and the circuit was mounted and all the desired aims and objectives were achieved.

5.2 System Deployment

This system can be deployed anywhere such as offices, homes, stations, companies etc provided there is usage of gas and things that may result to fire outbreak. It can be deployed in any country and works best in homes. This system works extensively for safety purposes and perseverance of humanity.

CHAPTER SIX

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

6.1 Summary

In the event of home smoke or gas leakage, your best defence is paramount important. Installing Smoke and Gas detector system has been observed to be the sure-fire way to make sure you are properly warned in the event of such a catastrophe. In the event of a smoke or gas leakage, you have only moments to evacuate your home, so give yourself the best opportunity to safely and quickly get you and your loved ones out by installing smoke and gas detectors.

6.1.1 Limitations

Though there were many challenges which I encountered in the course of this project but there were outstanding ones which seemed to weigh me down, though later persisted and achieve what I had wanted to achieve. These includes; the designing of the project circuit. During the designing of the circuits, I encountered problems like trying to make sure that my components (Arduino Nano, MQ2 sensor, Led pins etc) are making contact with the board without the bending of its pins.

Connecting of its wires appropriately was another challenge which most times wrong connections was made at the wrong points. Another challenge was that after the overall implementation of the circuit the green Led which was expected to come up never did indicating that something was still wrong somewhere.

Constructing the packaging of the system was another biggest challenge that I encountered so far.

However, these problems were made easy by my supervisor I consulted who enlightened me more and put me through.

6.1.2 Conclusion

The main objective of this project has been to design a circuit that detects smoke or leakage of gas and consequently triggers an alarm. This objective was met since the systems works effectively. As the smoke or gas detected in the environment varied, the serial monitor displayed the quantity constantly in particles per million (ppm) which sends an analog signal to the sensor if a given smoke or gas preset critical valuen is exceeded.

With the smoke or gas below the preset critical value, the green LED was on and the red LED was off. With the smoke or gas detected above the preset critical value, the green LED was off while the red LED was flashed and alarm is triggered “SMOKE OR GAS DETECTED”.

This system can be of great use in domestic as well as industrial settings to detect smoke or leakage of gas and alert people on an impending fire since smoke or leakage of gas is a precursor for fire, instead of relying on heat/temperature sensors which sounds alarm when the fire has already started. This can go a long way in helping to save human life. This system can also be used to detect and deter smokers in areas where smoking is prohibited.

The cost of implementing this system is relatively low since the components used are relatively cheap and are easily available in the market. The single microcontroller can be used to interface several sensors with alarms located in different locations as long as more pins are freed for multiple inputs multiple outputs.

6.1.2 Recommendation

Human safety is a very crucial aspect in both domestic and industrial setting; hence use of smoke and gas sensors is inevitable in addition to other more sophisticated security systems.

This system should be placed in a cool and dry place in order to ensure a longer life span. It should also be placed in a high place in the room and in the direction of the window where there is most likely to be the direction of the wind to facilitate the contact of the sensor with the smoke and gas. The system should be well positioned in a place that its alarm can be easily heard.

Lastly, method of reset of the switch has been explored in this project to enable the user reset the system once it has been attended to in case there was incident detected by the system that may have triggered the blowing of the alarm via the buzzer.

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APPENDIX 1**SOURCE CODE SAMPLE**

```
int redLed = 9;

int greenLed = 13;

int buzzer = 6;

int buzzerA0 = A5;

int sensorThresgas = 100;

int sensorThressmoke = 40;

void setup()

{

  pinMode (redLed, OUTPUT);

  pinMode (greenLed, OUTPUT);

  pinMode (buzzer, OUTPUT);

  pinMode (buzzerA0, INPUT);

  Serial.begin (9600);

}

void loop() {

int analogSensor = analogRead(buzzerA0);

Serial.print("Pin A0: ");

Serial.println(analogSensor);

if (analogSensor >sensorThresgas)

{
```

```
digitalWrite(redLed, HIGH);  
digitalWrite(greenLed, LOW);  
//digitalWrite(buzzer,HIGH);  
tone (buzzer, 1000);  
}  
else if (analogSensor >=40)  
{  
digitalWrite(redLed,HIGH);  
tone (buzzer, 1000);  
//digitalWrite(buzzer,HIGH);  
delay(100);  
//digitalWrite(greenLed,LOW);  
noTone (buzzer);  
delay(100);  
}  
else  
{  
digitalWrite (redLed, LOW);  
digitalWrite (greenLed, HIGH);  
noTone (buzzer);  
}  
Delay (100);  
}
```

APPENDIX II

ARDUINO SOFTWARE IDE

The screenshot displays the Arduino IDE interface with a project named "ProjectCode" open. The code in the editor is as follows:

```
int sensorThres = 203;

void setup() {
  pinMode (redLed, OUTPUT);
  pinMode (greenLed, OUTPUT);
  pinMode (buzzer, OUTPUT);
  pinMode (buzzerAD, INPUT);
  Serial.begin (9600);
}

void loop() {
  int analogSensor = analogRead(buzzerAD);

  Serial.print("Pin AD: ");
  Serial.println(analogSensor);
  if (analogSensor > sensorThres)
  {
    digitalWrite(redLed, HIGH);
    digitalWrite(greenLed, LOW);
    tone (buzzer, 1000, 200);
  }
  else
  {
    digitalWrite (redLed, LOW);
    digitalWrite (greenLed, HIGH);
    noTone (buzzer);
  }
  delay(100);
}
```

Below the code editor, a status bar indicates "Done compiling." and provides memory usage statistics: "Sketch uses 3,038 bytes (9%) of program storage space. Maximum is 30,720 bytes. Global variables use 219 bytes (10%) of dynamic memory, leaving 1,829 bytes for local variables. Maximum is 2,048 bytes." The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the system tray with the time 17:04 and date 11/16.

Fig 12: The coding interface of the system

APPENDIX 111

DIFFERENT VIEWS OF THE PACKAGED SYSTEM

